

Co-axial electrospinning for stabilization of amorphous solid dispersions

Version 4

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Co-axial electrospinning for stabilization of amorphous solid dispersions", No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0062.

In this project amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs) of active pharmaceutical molecule empagliflozin are explored. The dispersions are prepared using classic approaches and co-axial electrospinning. The project investigates:

- the polymer type, solvent type, drug to polymer ratio, and technological parameters on the solid-state of ASD;
- effect of surface-area-to-volume ratio on the kinetic stabilization and the dissolution profile of empagliflozin ASD;
- the empagliflozin ASD stabilization against degradation factors as a function of drug-polymer interaction and nanofiber structure properties.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience
Facility project "Internal and
External Consolidation of the
University of Latvia" (No.
5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Roman Viter (0000-0002-9996-041X), Artis Kons (0000-0002-4055-
8442)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Co-axial electrospinning for stabilization of amorphous solid dispersions](#)

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Contact: [Berzins Agris \(agris.berzins@lu.lv\)](mailto:berzins.agris@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

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3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-11-29

4. Templates

Descriptions

DSC traces

DSC traces of ASD prepared using different techniques

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Determine stability of the prepared ASDs, compare different preparation techniques.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No existing data have been identified.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

DSC, DSC/TG

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the research in scientific journal.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Agris Bērziņš (0000-0002-4149-8971)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

XRPD patterns

XRPD patterns of ASD prepared using different techniques

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

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20

MB

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XRPD, XRD

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